

CLINICAL - GENEALOGICAL ANALYSIS OF MUCOVISCIDOSIS

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It has been discovered that a low diagnostic level resulted in revealing the cases of mucoviscidosis, primarily in the families having affected or deceased sibs. This dependence on diagnosis results in a significant shift in a sample which evades correction. This error of the sample was precluded when families to be analysed were selected by the first effected child. Segregation analysis of 42 families by Weinberg's proband method has revealed a complete concordance with autosomic recessive inheritance as the portion of the affected was $25.0 \pm 2.21\%$. This approach has made it possible to handle the incomplete sample as unselected for which the correction techniques applicable to a complete sample can be used.

It is quite possible to assume that this diagnostic dependence can influence the results of segregation analysis of other hereditary diseases with broad clinical polymorphism.

Autosomal-recessive type of inheritance of mucoviscidosis is admitted by the majority of investigators (Danks et al., 1965; Crow, 1965 and others).

Earlier, however, some authors discovered the increase in the number of the affected persons in families with mucoviscidosis (Baumann, 1958; Roberts, 1960; Bemheim et al., 1961; Mastella and Montenovesi, 1964). On this basis a dominant form of mucoviscidosis, beside the recessive one, was postulated.

Analysis of the data obtained by Baumann (1958), Roberts (1960), Steinberg and Brown (1960) showed that the observed deviation was due to the inadequate statistical analysis of the obtained information.

Using more adequate statistical methods, Brunecky (1972) also failed to find full accordance with the expected 25% and pointed out that even the slightest increase in the ratio of affected persons must be explained.

In the present report we wish to analyse the causes leading to non-random samples of clinical materials not submitted to correction.

In the work the results of the clinical-genealogical analysis of 106 families ascertained by living or dead children with mucoviscidosis are used. Thirty-six families with one child each have been excluded from the analysis as they were considered to carry no information.

The obtained sample of families was estimated as an incomplete one with the method for single ascertainment (Cain C. 2012; Krasovski S. A. et al., 2012;).

The incomplete method for single ascertainment has not shown the correspondence to the autosomal-recessive type of inheritance, as the ratio of affected persons was $42.1 \pm 4.5\%$.

The significant increase in the ratio of affected persons in the sample may either suggest a different type of inheritance or the existence of some additional factors which had their influence on the sample (Kapustina, T. 2001.; Dumo C. et al., 2002).

The absence of the inheritance of the disease through generations, and, as a rule, the absence of the disease in semi-sibs contradicted the dominant type of inheritance (Erlinge D.2011). Consequently, some additional factors distorting the sample which could not be studied by the existing correction methods had to be sought.

First of all we have carried out the analysis of the accordance between the observed parts of families with different numbers of affected children expected to belong to an autosomal-recessive type. The results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of the observed and expected distribution of the families with different numbers of children at by the registering method for single ascertainment of the affected persons with a recessive disease

No. of children in the family	No. of affected children	Probability of detecting the affected persons in a family	No. of families		Deviation of found from expected number	χ^2	Degree of freedom	p
			expected	observed				
2	1	0.75	33	30	<1.10	1.1	1	0.30
	2	0.25	11	14	>1.27			

3	1	0.5625	11.25	6	<1.87	5.6	1	0.012
	2	0.375	7.5	9	>1.20			
	3	0.0625	1.25	5	>4.0			
4	1	0.4218	1.26	0	—	Calculations have not been made because of the small number of observations		
	2	0.4218	1.26	0	—			
	3	0.1404	0.42	2	> 4.74			
	4	0.0156	0.05	1	>21.73			

As is seen in Table I, the highest difference in distribution of the families found and expected is observed for the families with the greater number of affected children. Since the expected distribution already implies the greater probability of detecting families with numerous affected persons, the received inadequacy was the evidence of the existence of some additional factors distorting the sample.

It may be assumed that the reason for the distortion of the sample lies in the way of diagnosing mucoviscidosis. It is known that the child having affected site would sooner be found to have a disease. This factor cannot but be reflected in the shift of the sample towards the families with a greater number of the affected persons.

To test this assumption we have chosen the families ascertained by the first affected person. Only 42 such families were found in our sample with two and more children.

Table 2. The expected and observed frequency of the affected persons in 42 families analysed by a priori method

No. of children	No. of families	No. of affected children		Dispersion
		expected	observed	
2	36	41.14	42	4.392
3	6	7.78	7	1.578
Total	42	48.92	49	5.97

The correction of the results in these families by a priori method is given in Table II. The expected part of affected children has been calculated by the formula:

$$r^s = \frac{p \cdot s \cdot ns}{1 - q^s}$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{5.97} = 2.44; D/\sigma < 2 \sigma$$

The results obtained show the random nature of choosing these families. Thus, using correction methods at incomplete registering, it is possible to study the proportion of the affected and unaffected children for establishing the type of inheritance.

The results of the segregation of the progeny by the family method of Weinberg are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Analysis of segregation of the progeny in 42 families with mucoviscidosis found by the first affected child (family method of Weinberg)

Total No. of children in the family	No. of families	No. of affected children	r(r-1)	r(s-1)	Dispersion
2	30	1	0	1	4.20
2	6	2	2	2	0.42
3	5	1	0	2	0.24
3	1	2	2	4	0.02
Total	42	49	14	56	4.88

$$P = \frac{\sum r(r-1)}{\sum r(s-1)} = \frac{14}{56} = 0.25$$

$$\sigma = \sqrt{4.88} = 2.21$$

Thus the obtained value $25 \pm 2.21\%$ is in accordance with the hypothesis of recessive inheritance and proves the approach to the estimation of the sample to be correct. The existence of the factor of diagnostic dependence in

family forms may bring a distortion in segregational relations in the families with the diseases which do not have a full specific phenotype.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The genetic relations in families with mucoviscidosis found in the present clinical material do not correspond to the true segregational relations of the frequencies of the affected children.
2. One of the reasons which influence the increase of the frequency of affected children in families with mucoviscidosis on condition of incomplete detection is the diagnostic dependence in many cases upon the presence of the affected or dead sibs in a family,
3. The analysis of segregation in families found by the first affected child eliminates the diagnostic dependence and makes the sample random.
4. The established fact of diagnostic dependence upon the presence of the second patient in a family may be the natural cause of the deviation of segregational relations in some other hereditary diseases which are characterized by a wide clinical polymorphism.

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